

An Observational Study Assessing Role of Ultrasound Elastography in the Evaluation of Breast LesionsPriyanka Raj¹, Pradeep Kumar², Sanjeev Suman³, V.S.Prasad⁴¹Senior Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India⁴Professor and HOD, Department of Radiodiagnosis, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to evaluate the role of ultrasound elastography in the evaluation of breast lesions.**Methods:** The present study was a prospective observational study conducted in Department of Radiodiagnosis. Study period was one year. During study period total 100 patients underwent ultrasound elastography examination followed by core needle/surgical biopsy for histopathological study.**Results:** On histopathological study 78% lesions were benign, while 24% were malignant. Fibroadenoma (37%), fibrocystic changes (17%), galactocele (6%) and mastitis (7%) were common benign findings while invasive ductal carcinoma, mucinous carcinoma and invasive papillary carcinoma were malignant lesion findings. On ultrasound elastography score examination, scores of 1 (24%), 2 (39%), 3 (16%), 4 (7%) and 5 (14%) were noted. Scores 1 to 3 were considered benign and 4 and 5 malignant. On statistical analysis we calculated sensitivity (94/88%), specificity (83.62%), positive predictive value (93.57%), negative predictive value (85.35%) and accuracy (94.71%) of ultrasound elastography with histopathological report.**Conclusion:** Ultrasound elastography is a useful non-invasive diagnostic modality in differentiating benign from malignant breast lesions thereby reduces waiting, cost, discomfort and anxiety of a biopsy.**Keywords:** Ultrasonography breast, elastography, biopsy, Breast Malignancy

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Introduction

Mammography and ultrasonography (US) are the diagnostic methods which have shown the highest sensitivity in the detection of breast cancer. However, both methods present some limitations. Mammography performed in dense breasts may often yield false-negative results. [1] US is sensitive in the detection of lesions, but specificity is poor as most solid lesions are benign. In order to obtain an acceptable specificity, various characteristics of the lesions must be evaluated according to the BI-RADS criteria defined by the American College of Radiology (ACR). [2] Unfortunately, the BI-RADS criteria generate a significant number of false positive results. [3] This limitation leads to an increase in biopsies with a cancer “detection rate” of only 10%–30%. [4,5]

Many biopsies are performed in benign lesions causing discomfort to the patients and increased costs.

To overcome these limitations and obtain a more accurate characterization of breast lesions, US elastography was introduced. This technique combines US technology with the basic physical principles of elastography. US elastography is noninvasive and assesses tissue deformability by providing information on the elasticity. [6,7] It is based on the premise that there are significant differences in the mechanical properties of tissues that can be detected by applying an external mechanical force. [8,9]

Elasticity is the property of a body or substance that enables it to be deformed when it is subject to

an external force and resume its original shape or size when the force is removed. Different tissues are expected to respond differently according to the specific elastic modulus. [10] Tissue deformation is inversely proportional to the stiffness of the material, and response time (i.e. return to the natural condition) varies as a function of the histotype. [11] In general, adipose tissue is more easily deformed, and fibrous tissue returns to the initial condition more slowly than adipose or muscle tissue. [12]

Elastography is a non-invasive imaging technique in which local tissue strains are measured directly or indirectly by application of external stress. The tissue displacement is measured and a calculation of tissue stiffness is made based on tissue displacement. [13] Shear-wave elastography (SWE) reduces operator dependency which was encountered previously in free hand elastography. [14] A quantitative assessment of viscoelastic properties of tissue is obtained by inducing mechanical vibrations through a focused beam, which is expressed as Young's modulus or displayed as a color overlay of the lesion. [15] SWE is reported to have excellent diagnostic performance in distinguishing benign breast masses from malignant lesions. [16]

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the role of ultrasound elastography in the evaluation of breast lesions.

Materials and Methods

The present study was a prospective observational study conducted in Department of Radiodiagnosis, PMCH, Patna, Bihar, India. Study period was one year. During study period total 100 patients underwent ultrasound elastography examination followed by core needle/surgical biopsy for histopathological study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Female with suspected breast lesions on ultrasound/ clinical examination, later underwent core-needle biopsy or surgical biopsy with conclusive histopathologic diagnosis

Exclusion Criteria

- Already diagnosed cases, history of breast malignancy, recurrent lesions
- Inconclusive histopathology reports
- Not willing to participate

Patients were referred from department of general surgery for ultrasonography evaluation and department of pathology helped to get final histopathology reports.

Procedure was explained and a written informed consent was taken from patients. Demographic, clinical details were noted. Elastography examinations were performed using an Antares ultrasound system (Siemens Medical Solutions, Mountain View, CA) with integrated elastography software (eSie Touch elasticity imaging) and a multifrequency linear transducer (VFX13-5). Elastography image acquisition was performed by single radiologists with more than 10 years of experience in breast sonography and previously trained on breast elastography. For the elastography examination, the region of interest was superimposed semi transparently on the B-histopathologic diagnoses obtained from core-needle biopsy, or surgical biopsy, depending on the case. Details were noted in Microsoft excel sheet. Statistical analysis was done using descriptive statistics.

Results

Table 1: Final diagnosis of core needle/surgical biopsy results

Diagnosis	N	%
Benign	78	78
Fibroadenoma	37	37
Fibrocystic changes	17	17
Mastitis	7	7
Galactocele	6	6
Cyst	6	6
Abscess	5	5
Duct ectasia	3	3
Lactating adenoma	1	1
Phylloid tumor	1	1
Malignant	14	14
Invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC)	8	8
Mucinous carcinoma	3	3
Invasive papillary carcinoma (IPC)	3	3

On histopathological study 78% lesions were benign, while 24% were malignant. Fibroadenoma (37%), fibrocystic changes (17%), galactocele (6%) and mastitis (7%) were common benign findings while invasive ductal carcinoma, mucinous carcinoma and invasive papillary carcinoma were malignant lesion findings.

Table 2: Elastography score and histopathological diagnosis

Elastography score	Benign	Malignant	Total
1	24	0	24
2	39	0	39
3	11	5	16
4	1	6	7
5	0	14	14
Total	75	25	100

On ultrasound elastography score examination, scores of 1 (24%), 2 (39%), 3 (16%), 4 (7%) and 5 (14%) were noted. Scores 1 to 3 were considered benign and 4 and 5 malignant.

Table 3: Statistical values

Sensitivity	TP/(TP+FN)	94.88 %
Specificity	TN/(TN+FP)	83.62 %
Positive Predictive Value	TP/(TP+FP)	93.57 %
Negative Predictive Value	TN/(TN+FN)	85.35 %
Accuracy	(TP+TN)/(TP+TN+FP+FN)	93.71 %

On statistical analysis we calculated sensitivity (94/88%), specificity (83.62%), positive predictive value (93.57%), negative predictive value (85.35%) and accuracy (94.71%) of ultrasound elastography with histopathological report.

Discussion

Breast cancer is the most common cancer diagnosed in women globally and the second most common malignancy overall, after lung cancer. [17,18] The incidence of breast cancer has been on the rise over the last few decades. The incidence of breast cancer is the highest in Pakistan (50.1/100,000). [19] Data collected from 1995-1997 shows that breast cancer accounts for almost one-third of all female cancers in Karachi. [19] With more than half the population at risk, the incidence of breast cancer has alarmingly increased over the last few decades. [20] Breast cancer is uncommon before age 25 but the risk steadily increases with age, doubling every 10 years until menopause and slows dramatically afterwards. [21]

Elasticity is one of the important characteristics of tissues that may change under the influence of pathologic processes, such as inflammation and tumor development. Usually, a malignant lesion tends to be harder than a benign lesion because of its high cellularity and surrounding tissue desmoplasia. [22,23] Benign lesions on SE appear similar to the adjacent tissue and have a smaller diameter than on B-mode USG images. [24] Malignant tumours have reduced elasticity and also display larger dimensions on elastography due to accompanying desmoplastic reaction. [25] Aysar S K [26] studied 80 patients, 31 breast lesions were malignant and 49 were benign. B-mode ultrasound

was performed, and the lesions were categorized agreeing to the (BI-RADS) where chi-square statistical test uncovered that BI-RADS categories were essentially expanded among malignant cases ($P < 0.001$). On histopathological study 78% lesions were benign, while 24% were malignant. Fibroadenoma (37%), fibrocystic changes (17%), galactocele (6%) and mastitis (7%) were common benign findings while invasive ductal carcinoma, mucinous carcinoma and invasive papillary carcinoma were malignant lesion findings. [27]

On ultrasound elastography score examination, scores of 1 (24%), 2 (39%), 3 (16%), 4 (7%) and 5 (14%) were noted. Scores 1 to 3 were considered benign and 4 and 5 malignant. On statistical analysis we calculated sensitivity (94/88%), specificity (83.62%), positive predictive value (93.57%), negative predictive value (85.35%) and accuracy (94.71%) of ultrasound elastography with histopathological report. While Kumar AMS²⁷ noted that sensitivity, specificity and diagnostic accuracy of B-mode USG was calculated to be 71.74%, 90.91% and 81.11% and that for elastography was 95.65%, 68.18% and 82.22% respectively. They concluded, elastography may complement conventional B-mode USG to improve the diagnostic performance, which helps to reduce false-positive results and therefore is useful in avoiding unnecessary breast biopsy. Ultrasound has been proven to improve diagnostic sensitivity when added to screening mammography in high-risk women with dense breasts. However, the downside was an increased false-positive rate and lower positive predictive value. [28]

Conclusion

Ultrasound elastography is a useful non-invasive diagnostic modality in differentiating benign from malignant breast lesions thereby reduces waiting, cost, discomfort and anxiety of a biopsy.

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